

DETERMINANTS OF CAPITAL FLIGHT: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the determinants of capital flight from Nigeria using time series data from 1990 to 2022. The study was motivated by the need to proffer measures for curbing capital flight from Nigeria. The method of data analysis was the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) regression technique; which was informed by the mixed order of integration of the variables in the model. Empirical results revealed that regulatory quality, corruption, and inflation rate were the major determinants of capital flight from Nigeria since they exhibited significant short-run and long-run influence on capital flight. GDP growth rate, exchange rate and external debt were short-run determinants of capital flight whereas electricity supply was found to be a long-run determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. Some policy recommendations were offered to curtail capital flight and improve macroeconomic performance in Nigeria; these included the need to enforce open reporting of suspicious financial transactions by banks and forcing defaulters to pay a fine that is equal to the amount involved in such fraudulent transactions or have their operation license withdrawn.

Key Words: Capital flight, determinants, policy options, and Nigeria.

Introduction

Capital flight from Nigeria has become a pressing economic issue, undermining the nation's financial stability and hampering development efforts. The movement of capital across international borders is motivated by socio-economic factors. Investors often transfer their capital from their home country to foreign countries in response to unpleasant and undesirable conditions that could jeopardise their business successes in their home country. It could be due to macroeconomic mismanagement which could manifest in high tax rates, high inflation rates, lax legal framework for protecting civil freedom and property rights, and prevalence of political unrest among others. Capital is attracted to countries with more conducive business environments. The cross-border movement of capital is central to the phenomenon of capital flight. Economics dictionary of defines capital flight as large scale and sudden movements of capital from a country by residents or foreigners; maintaining that capital flight is caused by fear of public disorder, fear of confiscation or drastically increased taxation, fear of rapid inflation leading to loss of its value by the country's currency.

Ndikumana and Boyce (2021) defined capital flight as a residual of the balance of payments consisting of discrepancies between recorded foreign exchange inflows and recorded uses of these inflows. They maintained that capital flight manifests itself in an economy through illegal activities such as money laundering and trade misinvoicing (over-invoicing of import and under-invoicing of export). This implies that capital flight represents outflows of financial resources which are not recorded in official records of the transactions between the country and the rest of the world. The main record of such transaction is the balance of payments (BOP). The balance of payments records the inflows of foreign exchange into the country and their uses. The main inflow comprises public external debts and foreign direct investment. The main uses of foreign exchange are the coverage of the current account deficits and net additions to foreign reserves.

The phrase 'capital flight' has been used across industrialized and developing nations. Some scholars see capital outflows from wealthy nations as foreign direct investment while referring to the same actions by citizens of a developing country as capital flight (Ajayi, 2012). Capital flight connotes a loss of financial resources from the domestic financial market and it is at odds with the interest, aims and aspirations of the domestic economy from which the capital flies.

In this study, in line with the views of scholars such as Ndikumana and Boyce (2021), Mazadu *et al.* (2022), Uguru *et al.* (2014), Rahmon (2017), Oladimeji *et al.* (2022), Benjamin and Christian (2020), we define capital flight as an illicit outflow of financial resources from a country; which are not recorded in the official government statistics. Since such capital outflows escape government records, government of the country from which capital flies cannot tract investment generated with the capital in the rest of the world; and this denies the government the opportunity of generating tax revenue through the process. This definition distinguishes capital flight from foreign direct investment and other capital flows which are usually documented in government statistics.

Capital often flies from less-developed countries to more-developed ones rather than the other way around. Thus, the impacts of capital flight tend to be more severe in less-developed countries. Capital flight implies loss of a critical factor of production and the economy of the country from which capital flies are deprived of essential resources for economic growth and development. For this reason, the issue of capital flight from African countries and Nigeria in particular has gained substantial attention in academic and the policy arena in recent years, especially in the context of the debate on financing sustainable growth and development. One of the major cited constraints to economic development in Nigeria is the lack of adequate financial resources. According to the neoclassical growth theory, an economy's capital accumulation and the manner in which people use the capital influences the growth rate of the economy.

African countries are being deprived of funds essential for fostering economic growth and development due to capital flight. According to estimates from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Africa loses up to \$50 billion annually as a result of money laundering, tax evasion, diverted funds, offshore investments, and other forms of capital flight. The African governments are deprived of the required capital resources for economic growth and development due to such high levels of capital outflows and loss of revenues. More than any other region on the globe, Sub-Saharan Africa struggles

with this problem, and these nations lose more money to capital flight than they receive in form of aid or foreign private investment combined (Jawaid, 2014).

Repatriations of flight capital will add to resource inflows such as overseas remittances, portfolio investments, official development assistance (ODA), and foreign direct investment (FDI). Reversing capital flight could assist Nigeria reduce her expenditure-financing gap. The essential questions, however, are: what is the nature and degree of capital flight in Nigeria? What incentives exist to discourage capital flight and encourage its reversal to the Nigerian economy? A genuine focus on these issues will lower foreign debts, boost investor confidence, increase investment, and reduce unemployment rate and its negative repercussions in the Nigerian economy.

Sustainable development may not be realized in Nigeria if sufficient resources are not mobilized for domestic production. These funds are required for the provision of social services such as health care, infrastructure, education. Capital flight inhibits sustainable development in Nigeria by increasing reliance on foreign resources, which most often than not exposes the economy to external shocks. Therefore, Nigeria's economy requires conscious governmental actions to reverse the capital flight trend. This can be achieved by first identifying the causes of capital flight from Nigeria. Therefore, the objective of this study is to investigate the determinants of capital flight from Nigeria.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature

The determinants of capital flight are factors that would make investors or asset owners believe that their money is not secure where it is or that it would be better off and yield higher interest elsewhere. Some of these ailments include instability in politics, low domestic interest rates, high inflation, huge external debt, financial liberalization, lagged values of capital flight, and overvaluation of the domestic currency. These factors can be deduced from some theories such as investment diversion theory, debt-driven capital flight theory and portfolio choice theory.

Investment Diversion Theory

Kindleberger (1966) developed the investment diversion theory. According to the theory, investors (owners of capital) frequently withdraw their funds from nations that are already experiencing or are expected to experience macroeconomic or political instability. The business environment in emerging nations like Nigeria is plagued by numerous challenges, including excessive taxes, insufficient power supply, poor state of infrastructure, political, religious, and ethnic issues, high rate of inflation, and exchange rate problem. These are the alleged explanations offered by this hypothesis for the capital flight that developing countries experience. Accordingly, the theory contends that due to the macroeconomic and political unpredictability in developing nations and the concurrent availability of better investment opportunities in developed nations, such as high foreign interest rates, a wide range of financial instruments, political and economic stability, and favourable tax, investors divert limited capital resources from developing nations to developed ones.

Debt-Driven Capital Flight Theory

The debt-driven capital flight theory is an expansion of the investment diversion theory and a refinement of Krugman's (1988) debt overhang hypothesis. According to the debt overhang hypothesis, debt is a future burden since predicted repayment frequently exceeds

the borrowing country's capacity for repayment. The debt-driven capital flight theory contends that external debt raises the demand for foreign currency as a result of debt repayment, which depreciates the currency from which external debt repayment is expected. From the theory, one of the drivers of capital flight from Nigeria is the country's enormous external debt. Capital flight reduces motivation to save and invest. It is assumed that with high levels of foreign debt, there will likely be exchange rate devaluations, fiscal crises, and a predisposition for expropriating assets and crowding out of domestic capital in order to pay off the debt. Together, the debt-driven and investment-driven theories propose a mutually reinforcing interdependence between capital flight, growth, and foreign debt.

Portfolio Choice Theory

The portfolio choice theory developed by Markowitz in 1959 identifies risk aversion and the desire to maximise return as the driving forces behind investment and capital flow placement decisions. The idea proposed in this theory is that the entry or outflow of capital is determined by factors such as risk and return. These factors that influence investment and capital flight suggest that the investor who decides how much money moves between nations is motivated by their ideal choice of low risk and high return on investment. Given the current commercial risks in Nigeria caused by the nation's unstable political climate and the attendant socioeconomic problems, rational investors are likely to transfer their wealth to nations with stable political environments.

Numerous empirical studies have been done on the reasons behind capital flight. Results vary, but with some degree of empirical consistency because capital flight is measured differently and econometric methods and parameters vary. For the years 1980 to 2004, Yalta and Yalta (2012) looked into the relationship between financial liberalization and the amount of capital flight in 21 developing market economies. Using Granger causality test and dynamic panel data estimation model, their empirical findings revealed no link between capital flight and financial liberalization. They also found out that capital flight's historical levels significantly influenced its present-day levels. Similarly, Dim and Ezenekwe (2014) who investigated the socioeconomic factors that influence capital flight in Nigeria also found out that the lag values of capital flight had significant impact on the current value of capital flight. Similar result was also reported by Ndikumana and Boyce (2003) who in their study of the determinants of capital flight from 30 sub-Saharan African countries noted that capital flight demonstrated a high level of persistence as past values of capital flight was associated with its current values.

Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique, Mazadu *et al.* (2022) examined the factors that contribute to capital flight from Nigeria. Annual data from 1981 to 2018 were used in the study. The study showed that GDP growth rate, financial development, external debt and high rate of inflation were significant long- and short-run determinants of capital flight from Nigeria. The researchers came to the conclusion that Nigerian governments must provide a secure macroeconomic and financial environment, and make sure that all borrowed money from abroad is put toward worthwhile ventures with higher returns.

Tarawalie and Jalloh (2021) looked into the causes of capital flight in Sierra Leone as well as the relationship between some macroeconomic variables and capital flight. The researchers used quarterly data spanning from 2000 Quarter1 to 2019 Quarter1 using the Granger causality paradigm for data analysis. They used the autoregressive distributed lag

(ARDL) technique. The results of the bound test supported the existence of cointegration, and the long-run analysis showed that the real effective exchange rate, corruption, and external debt were Sierra Leone's primary drivers of capital flight. The real effective exchange rate, corruption, external debt, and capital flight were all found to be positively correlated. External debt and capital flight indicate a bi-directional causal relationship, according to the results of the Granger causality test. However, inflation and exchange rate both show one-way causality.

Dim and Ezenekwe (2014) investigated the socioeconomic factors that influence capital flight from Nigeria. Two measures of capital flight were modelled against several socioeconomic factors identified in the literature: the hot money technique and the residual method. To identify the key causes of capital flight from Nigeria, fully modified ordinary least squares and an error correction mechanism were used. The researchers specified that capital flight is a function of exchange rate, inflation rate, external debt, gross domestic product growth rate and lagged values of capital flight. Their analysis showed that the determinants of capital flight from Nigeria were exchange rate, external debt, and lagged values of capital flight. They asserted that in the absence of effective macroeconomic policies to tackle these concerns, there will be a higher degree of capital flight, very little domestic investment, high levels of poverty, and an elusive pursuit of economic progress.

The determinants of capital flight were examined by Ndikumana and Boyce (2003) from 30 sub-Saharan African countries, including 24 countries categorized as severely indebted low-income countries, between 1970 and 1996. The econometric analysis, which used fixed effect analysis with pooled annual data, revealed that external borrowing was positively and significantly related to capital flight, indicating that capital flight is, to a large extent, debt-fueled. They argued that capital flight also demonstrated a high level of persistence, as past capital flight was associated with both current and future capital flight.

In a study by Fang *et al.* (2010), a stepwise regression method for quantitative analysis was used to analyze the economic factors impacting China's capital flight. The findings indicated that capital flight had a negative relationship with financial deficit, foreign debt balance, and the interest rate difference between the United States and China, while financial repression increased capital flight and foreign direct investment aided China's capital flight. They said that the biggest factor encouraging China's capital flight was an interest rate differential (IRD). Foreign exchange reserves and economic growth rate have had a restraining influence on capital flight. Inflation rate had a negative link with capital flight.

Between 1971 and 2011, Salandy and Henry (2018) looked at the factors that contributed to capital flight from Trinidad and Tobago. The study found that the lagged external debt, lagged capital flight, external debt, GDP growth, interest rate differential, and excess liquidity are the main contributors to capital flight. This was determined using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) and the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimate approaches. In another country study, the dynamic relationship between capital flight and macroeconomic fundamentals in Malaysia between 1992 and 2012 was examined by Auzairy *et al.* (2017). Co-integration and vector auto-regression (VAR) techniques of estimation were employed in the study. The Consumer Price Index (CPI), GDP, interest rate, and currency rate were found to be the macroeconomic fundamentals that determine capital flight.

Moghadam *et al.* (2003) investigation focused on capital flight, its causes, and how it affected the South East Asian currency crisis of the late 1990s. In order to determine the

political and economic factors that influence capital flight, an empirical model was constructed using panel data techniques. The degree of economic openness, the ratio of government budget surplus to GDP, which was believed to be a measure of economic stability, and the ratio of military expenditure to GDP, which was taken to be a sign of political instability, were among the factors determining capital flight that were evaluated in the study. As would be predicted, political instability and openness levels were positively correlated with capital flight. Capital flight and government budget excess have a bad relationship. The researchers highlighted corruption as one factor that may have a big impact on the flow of capital internationally. Therefore, increased transparency of accounting processes in the public and private sectors is necessary to reduce the disruptive effects of capital flight on the emerging economies.

From 1992 to 2008, Zhanfeng and Xiaojuan (2010) examined the connection between capital flight and foreign direct investment in China. Correlation analysis was used to explore the relationship in China, and the findings showed that there was a substantial positive correlation between them. According to the researchers, the correlation between capital flight and foreign direct investment was positive, indicating that capital flight in developing nations was somewhat encouraged by foreign direct investment. The researchers claimed that the discriminating regulations between domestic and foreign capital are, to a considerable extent, to blame for the domestic capital flight from China, rather than the deterioration of the investment environment.

Harrigan *et al.* (2002) used time series data from 1970 to 1996 to research the factors that contribute to capital flight in Malaysia. In the investigation, they employed the cointegration and ordinary least square (OLS) regression techniques. The results of econometric study showed that capital flight, currency rate fluctuations, changes in external debt, real GDP growth, and foreign direct investment all have a long-term relationship. Foreign direct investment had a negative link with capital flight, whereas exchange rate movement, changes in external debts, and GDP growth had favorable relationships. They advised the national authorities to promote not only exchange rate stability but also a reduction in the accumulation of external debt, sustainable economic growth, and increased FDI.

Agbaje (2014) analyzed Nigeria's twelve years of democratic governance while analyzing the connection between political gains, capital outflows, and economic growth. The only type of analysis used was descriptive. In Nigeria, he found that the economic mix of political earnings functions more like a cog than as a stimulant for growth. The author presented strategies by which local reinvestment of political earnings could be encouraged to contribute to current attempts at rapid national growth after identifying constitutional, sociological, and other systemic disincentives as important inhibiting factors.

Bosupeng *et al.* (2019) studied the impact of exchange rate mismatch on outward capital flight in Botswana from 1980 to 2015. The study used the Toda and Yamamoto (1995) method to Granger causality and the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach to cointegration. Foreign reserves, GDP growth, inflation rate, real interest rate differentials, foreign aid, trade openness, external debt, and real exchange rate were among the factors used in the study to determine the causes of capital flight. They claimed that Botswana's currency misalignment was the result of current account imbalances, and that trade openness is the

most significant factor in determining capital flight from Botswana. This suggests that exportable goods were undervalued, resulting in net capital outflows. They maintained that in the long-run, when the currency is overvalued, the volume of capital flight through trade misinvoicing declines and increasing foreign reserves does not reduce outward capital flight. However, when the currency is undervalued, the volume of capital flight through trade misinvoicing increases and foreign reserves reduce outward capital flight. They recommended that Botswana should also implement capital controls to limit capital smuggling and maintain monetary autonomy.

Forson *et al.* (2017) examined the short- and long-term determinants of capital flight in Ghana using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) estimating method. The long-run and short-run results showed that capital flight is decreased in Ghana by real GDP growth rate, higher real domestic interest rates relative to international interest rates, financial development, excellent governance, and strong property rights, whereas increased capital flight is caused by external debt to GDP. Lagged financial development and lagged external debt to GDP, however, had adverse and advantageous effects in the short term, respectively. The researchers advised the government to implement more pro-growth measures and turn to local borrowing to lower the country's external debt. They also suggested that the Central Bank of Ghana should advance the expansion of the financial sector and maintain competitive domestic interest rates.

Akanbi (2015) used the Engle-Grant two-step process to look at the factors that contributed to capital flight from Nigeria between 1981 and 2010. The study discovered that each of the explanatory variables, including investment, interest rates, and defence spending, had direct relationship with capital flight. The researcher maintained that money meant for stabilization and development is lost through capital flight. Similarly, Aderibigbe *et al.* (2019) used the Johansen Co-integration approach to study the determinants of capital flight and their impact on tax bases in Nigeria from 1981 to 2015. The study found that external borrowing, exchange rate, interest rate differentials, capital account openness, natural resource endowment, and stock of external debt are key short-run and long-run determinants of capital flight in Nigeria, and that capital flight works against expansion of tax base. They recommended that government should use fiscal discipline as well as effective monetary policies to control the volume of external borrowing so as to reduce capital flight and minimise its effects on the economy of Nigeria.

Onodungo *et al.* (2014) used a two-step Engle-Granger Approach to analyze the impact of changes in the exchange rate, trade balance, real GDP growth, interest rate differential, index of the political climate, and manufacturing output on capital flight in Nigeria from 1970 to 2010. The researchers discovered that, with the exception of the currency rate and the index of the local political environment, all other explanatory variables have positive correlation with capital flight over a one-period lag.

Anetor (2019) conducted a study on the macroeconomic factors influencing capital flight from the sub-Saharan African region using evidence from the countries in that region between the years 1981 and 2015. Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model techniques were used to identify these macroeconomic determinants of capital flight from the region. The results of the investigation demonstrated that economic growth had a strong adverse association with capital flight over the long and short terms and that the major determinants of capital flight from the region included interest rate differentials, inflation rate and external

debts. The researcher advocated for policies aimed at tackling the root causes of capital flight from the region.

An econometric examination of the factors that contributed to capital flight in Bangladesh between 1973 and 2013 was conducted by Uddin, *et al.* (2017). They employed ordinary least squares (OLS) regression technique and discovered that foreign direct investment, external debt, interest rate differentials, foreign reserves, and current account surplus are the main contributors to capital flight. The study also found a significant positive association between the change in external debt and capital flight as well as the interest rate disparity.

Azziz *et al.* (2014) used time series data from 1973 to 2013 to analyze the factors that contribute to capital flight from Bangladesh. To estimate the indicators of capital flight, the ordinary least squares (OLS) method of analysis was used. The main contributors to capital flight were found to be external debt, foreign direct investment, and foreign reserves. Also, their statistical analysis demonstrated that capital flight out of Bangladesh was primarily due to foreign debt, and they came to the conclusion that managing and using the external debt effectively would be a significant method to address the issue of capital flight in the country.

Despite the numerous empirical literatures on the determinants of capital flight from Nigeria, some key factors affecting Nigerian business environments and capable of influencing capital flight from Nigeria have not been considered in the previous studies. These factors include the regulatory quality of the Nigerian business environment and the issue of electricity supply which can influence business destination decisions. Therefore, this study constitutes an extension to the literature by examining regulatory quality and electricity supply as determinants of capital flight from Nigeria; factors which have been overlooked in previous studies. This addition provides a more comprehensive understanding of the underlying causes of capital flight in Nigeria.

Methodology

The ex-post facto (after-the-fact) research design was used for this study, as secondary sources of data were explored. The study adopts an econometric method of data analysis with annual time series data covering the period of 1981 to 2022. Auto Regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) regression technique is used for data analysis.

To investigate the determinants of capital flight from Nigeria, we applied a modified form of the model used by Dim and Ezenekwe (2014) in their study of the determinants of capital flight from Nigeria. They specified that capital flight (CAPF) is a function of lagged values of capital flight (L.CAPF), gross domestic product growth rate (GDPG), external debt (EXD), inflation rate (INFR) and exchange rate (EXR). The functional form of their model can be written as:

$$\text{CAPF} = f(\text{L.CAPF}, \text{GDPG}, \text{EXD}, \text{INFR}, \text{EXR}) \quad (\text{i})$$

Although the current values of macroeconomic variables are usually influenced by their past values, we drop the lagged value of capital flight (L.CAPF) from equation (i) because regressing it on its current values would mean an identity regression which can result in spurious regression results. This results in equation (ii) as follows:

$$\text{CAPF} = f(\text{GDPG}, \text{EXD}, \text{INFR}, \text{EXR}) \quad (\text{ii})$$

Where: CAPF, GDPG, EXD, INFR and, EXR are as earlier described. CAPF and

EXD are expressed as percentage of GDP. These are economic determinants of capital flight. In terms of political determinants of capital flight, we look at the influence of corruption (COR) and in terms of institutional determinants, we look at the effect of regulatory quality (REQ) and finally we look at energy requirements for business success which is proxy by index of electricity production (IEP). COR, REQ and IEP together capture the impact of business environment and the ease of doing business on capital flight in Nigeria.

By incorporating COR, REQ and IEP into equation (ii), we have equation (iii) thus:

$$CAPF = f(GDPG, EXD, INFR, EXR, COR, REQ, IEP) \quad (iii)$$

Where:

CAPF = Capital flight as a percentage of GDP

GDPG = Gross domestic product growth rate

EXD = External debt stock as a percentage of GDP

INFR = Inflation rate

EXR = Exchange rate

COR = Corruption, proxy by corruption perception index

REQ = Regulatory quality

IEP = Index of electricity production

An econometric form of equation (iii) is shown in equation (iv) which is our operational model; it is used to investigate the determinants of capital flight from Nigeria.

$$CAPF_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDPG_t + \beta_2 EXD_t + \beta_3 INFR_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 COR_t + \beta_6 REQ_t + \beta_7 IEP_t + \mu_t \quad (iv)$$

β_0 is the intercept term to be estimated, while $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ and β_7 are the coefficient estimates of the variables GDPG (-), EXD (+), INFR (+), EXR(+), COR (-), REQ (-) and IEP (-) respectively. The signs in parenthesis represent a priori expectations of each of the variables. None of the variables is logged since they are in rates or expressed as ratios (Saibu and Olagunji, 2006). Since our analytical technique involves the use of ARDL model, we show its functional form in equation (v) thus: $Y_t = \gamma_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \phi_i x_{t-i} + \gamma_t + \mu_t$ (v)

Where Y_t is the dependent variable as a function of its lag term Y_{t-i} and other explanatory variables x_{t-i} . p and q signify lag orders for the lagged variables in the model for independent and dependent variables respectively. On the other hand δ_i and ϕ_i coefficient of Y_{t-i} and x_{t-i} respectively. γ_t is the slope of the time trend. the error term μ_t is normally distributed around its mean of zero and it has a constant variance.

In equation (vi), we present the long-run ARDL model including the variables in our operational model thus:

$$CAPF_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta CAPF_{t-p} + \sum_{i=0}^n \omega GDPG_{t-p} + \sum_{i=0}^n \theta EXD_{t-p} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta INFR_{t-p} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta EXR_{t-p} + \sum_{i=0}^n \vartheta COR_{t-p} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Xi REQ_{t-p} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Upsilon IEP_{t-p} + \mu_t \quad (vi)$$

The variables CAPF, GDPG, EXD, INFR, EXR, COR, REQ and IEP are as earlier described. The constant term is α_0 whereas $\beta, \omega, \theta, \delta, \vartheta, \Xi, \Upsilon$ are the parameters to be estimated and μ_t is the white noise error term. The a priori expectations of the parameters are as specified in equation (iv); and model (vi) is performed to detect appropriate lags order of the variables, followed by the bound test.

Data for this study were collected from secondary sources. Gross Domestic Product growth rate (GDPG), inflation rate (INFR) were sourced from the World Bank Development Indicators. Data on regulatory quality (REQ) were sourced from World Governance Indicators. Data on corruption (COR); that is, corruption perception Index were sourced from

the website of Transparency International. Index of electricity production (IEP) was sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria's Annual Report and Statement of Accounts (Various Issues). Exchange rate (EXR) and external debt (EXD) were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin (2022). Data on capital flight (CAPF) was extracted from Ndikumana and Boyce (2021).

Findings and Discussion

Unit Root Test of Variables in the Model

The regression of non-stationary time series data can produce spurious results. To check for the existence of stationarity in the data used, we used Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test procedure while taking into consideration the three alternative assumptions of data generating processes: intercept, intercept with trend, and none. We present the result of the test in Table 1

Table 1 Unit Root Test Result of Variables in the Model Variable ADF Test Statistic 5% Critical Value Order of Integration

Variable	ADF Test Statistic	5% Critical Value	Order of Integration
EXR	3.127535	-2.935001	I(0)
CAPF	-5.307326	-2.935001	I(0)
EXD	-2.697226	-1.954414	I(1)
COR	-5.545171	-3.595026	I(1)
INFR	-3.300411	-2.935001	I(0)
REQ	-5.900721	-2.981038	I(1)
IEP	-5.166180	-2.981038	I(1)
RGDG	-3.203694	-2.936942	I(0)

Source: Computed by the researcher using E-views 10.0 (2024)

Table 2 shows that there are eight variables in the model; and four out of the eight variables were stationary at their levels. The four variables are: gross domestic product growth rate (GDPG), inflation rate (INFR), capital flight (CAPF) and exchange rate (EXR). They were integrated of order zero; that is $\sim I(0)$. This is known through their ADF test statistics which were in absolute terms greater than their 5% critical values. The remaining four variables – index of electricity production (IEP), regulatory quality (REQ), corruption (COR) and external debt (EXD) were stationary at their first differences. They were integrated of order one; that is $\sim I(1)$. This holds because their ADF test statistics became greater than their respective 5% critical values in absolute terms at their first differences. Since all the variables in the model are stationarity, there is no risk of obtaining spurious regressions. Next, we find out whether a long-run relationship exists among the variables in the model. Informed by the mixed order of integration of the variables, that is I(0) and I(1), use of Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model for estimation and the test for co-integration.

Co-integration Test of Variables in the Model

Following the stationarity test which revealed a mixed order of integration, the existence of long-run relationship among the variables in the model was examined using the ARDL bound test for co-integration; and the result as presented in Table 2 revealed the existence co-integration among the variables in the model.

Table 2 ARDL Bound Test for Co-integration

Test Statistic	Value	Sign. Level	Lower Bound I(0)	Upper Bound I(1)
F-Statistic	4.576	10%	2.03	3.13
K	7	5%	2.32	3.50
		1%	2.96	4.26

Source: Computed by the Researcher using E-views 10.0 (2024)

Table 2 shows that co-integration exists among the variables in the model; judging from the F-statistic result. The F-statistic value of 4.576 is greater than the lower and the upper bound values of 2.32 and 3.50 respectively at 5% level of significance. Even at 1% level of significance, the F-statistic value is still greater than the corresponding lower and upper bound values of 2.96 and 4.26 respectively. Therefore, co-integration existed among the variables in the model at 1% level of significance. This is an evidence of the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables in the model. Consequently, given capital flight as a response variable, there is need to examine the long-run and short-run determinants of capital flight from Nigeria in light of the explanatory variables in the model.

Long-run and Short-run Results

Given the established long-run relationship among the variables in the model, we present the long-run and short-run estimation results in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively. ARDL model simultaneously estimates the long-run and the short-run relationship among the variables. The short-run estimates show short-term dynamics, specifically how fast the system adjusts back to equilibrium after a shock. For each of the explanatory variables, their respective impact is examined in terms of the signs, magnitude and significance of the parameter estimates.

**Table 3: ARDL Long-run Estimation Result
Dependent Variable: Capital Flight (CAPF)**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDPG	-0.187479	0.219988	-0.852223	0.4123
INFR	0.561538	0.161357	3.480096	0.0382
EXR	-0.023329	0.021837	-1.068344	0.3082
IEP	-0.635194	0.329391	-1.928389	0.0510
REQ	-0.473064	0.233151	-2.029003	0.0674
COR	-0.680477	0.345690	-1.968461	0.0747
EXD	0.468246	0.319625	1.464987	0.1709

Source: Computed by the Researcher Using E-views 10.0 (2024)

**Table 4 ARDL Short-Run Estimation Result
Dependent Variable: Capital Flight (CAPF)**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GDPG)	-0.404204	0.136042	-2.971170	0.0509
D(INFR)	0.122451	0.055339	2.212731	0.0490
D(EXR)	-0.091052	0.026346	-3.456036	0.0054
D(IEP)	-0.008438	0.015401	-0.547860	0.5947
D(REQ)	-0.806696	0.141496	-5.701208	0.0001
D(COR)	-0.587361	0.153946	-3.815363	0.0029
D(EXD)	0.933534	0.272428	3.426720	0.0057
CointEq(-1)*	-0.641207	0.206365	-3.107148	0.0000

Source: Computed by the Researcher Using E-views 10.0 (2024)

Gross domestic product growth rate (GDPG) had a negative relationship with capital flight both in the short-run and in the long-run; however, only the short-run estimate was significant. The short-run results presented in Table 4 shows that GDPG had a negative coefficient of -0.40420 which is in conformity to its a priori expectation. Its t- statistic value of -2.9711 with the probability of 0.0509 implies that the estimate is significant at 5% level. The relationship is such that 1% point increase in GDPG reduces capital flight by 0.40% point. The empirical analysis revealed that an increase in gross domestic product growth rate leads to a decrease in capital flight in the short-run but this relationship became insignificant in the long-run. This implies that GDP growth is a short-run determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. This holds because in the short-run, GDP growth may lead to increased economic activity. Improved economic conditions enhance confidence in the domestic economy; which in turn attract foreign investors and reduce the incentive for domestic capital to flee. Investors might prefer to invest within the country where they perceive higher returns due to improved economic conditions. This finding is in tandem with the findings of many of the previous researchers on this issue such as Mazadu *et al.* (2022), Fang *et al.* (2010), Forson *et al.* (2017), Auzairy *et al.* (2017) and Anetor (2019) but at variance with the findings of other researchers such as Salandy and Henry (2018). The negative but insignificant relationship between GDP growth rate and capital flight in the long-run suggests that GDP growth alone cannot sustainably curtail capital flight; suggesting the need to address some structural problems in the economy. Over the long term, structural problems such as corruption, weak institutions, political instability and unfavourable business environment may continue to intensify capital flight regardless of GDP growth; thus making the negative relationship between capital flight and GDP growth rate to be insignificant.

Inflation rate (INFR) exhibited a positive and significant relationship with capital flight (CAPF) in the short-run and in the long-run; in line with its a priori expectation. The short-run coefficient of 0.1224 with the t-statistic value of 2.2127, and the probability of 0.0490 show that the estimate is significant at 5% level. This means that in the short-run, 1% point increase in the rate of inflation intensifies capital flight by 0.12% point. The long-run coefficient of INFR is 0.5615 and with its probability of 0.0382, the estimate is significant at 5% level. This implies that in the long-run, 1% point increase in the rate of inflation intensifies

capital flight by 0.56% point. Inflation rate is thus a short-run and long-run determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. This happens because in the short-run, inflationary pressures may signal economic instability, resulting in a loss of confidence in the domestic economy; thus leading to increased capital outflows. In the long-run, persistent inflation can erode the value of domestic assets. Thus, investors may seek to protect their wealth and achieve better returns in more stable environments. This makes foreign investment more appealing and leading to sustained capital flight. The finding suggests the need for Nigeria to tackle the underlying causes of inflation in the country such as poor state of infrastructures which can increase the cost of production, reduce the volume of production and lead to further increase in prices of goods and services through the operation of price mechanism. The finding is in tandem with the findings of Mazadu *et al.* (2022) Auzairy *et al.* (2017) and Anetor (2019) but contrary to the findings of Fang *et al.* (2010).

Against its positive a priori expectation, exchange rate (EXR) showed negative relationship with capital flight from Nigeria. This holds in the short-run and in the long-run; however, only the short-run estimate was significant. Table 5 shows that exchange rate had a short-run coefficient of -0.0911 with a t-statistic value of -3.4560; judging from its probability value of 0.0054, the estimate was significant at 1% level. This implies that increase in the amount of naira going for a dollar was associated with a reduction in capital flight. The relationship is such that a unit depreciation of naira reduced capital flight by 0.09% point. The significant relationship between exchange rate and capital flight in the short-run implies that exchange rate is a short-run determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. This implies that in the short-run, increase in the amount of naira per dollar (exchange rate depreciation) led to significant reduction in capital flight. This happens because as the naira depreciates, the cost of converting naira into foreign currencies rises. This makes foreign investments less attractive since the potential returns may not exceed the higher exchange cost. Moreover, investors who believe that naira will stabilize or appreciate in the near future might hold off on converting their capital into foreign currencies. In the long-run, the estimation was found to be insignificant; indicating that over the long period, changes in exchange rate do not have a lasting impact on capital flight. In the long-term, changes in capital flight may be more sensitive to some structural challenges in the economy than the exchange rate. Structural problems such as political instability, corruption, inadequate financial regulations can persist; thus intensifying capital flight regardless of exchange rate variations. The finding is in line with that of Auzairy *et al.* (2017), Harrigan *et al.* (2002) but at variance with the findings of some researchers such as Tarawalie and Jalloh (2021), Dim and Ezenekwe (2014).

Index of electricity production (IEP) conformed to its negative a priori expectation in the short-run and long-run. However, it had a significant estimate only in the long-run. The long-run coefficient was -0.6351 with the probability of 0.0510; thus, the estimate was significant at 1% level. This means that in the long-run, a unit increase index of electricity production will reduce capital flight by 0.64% point. This implies that IEP is a long-run determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. In the long term, consistent and reliable electricity supply becomes a key factor in investment decisions. This is because improved electricity supply leads to reduction in cost of production, enhance competitiveness, reduce incentive for capital flight and make Nigeria an attractive investment destination. The insignificant short-run estimate may be attributed to the fact that investors may require some time to adjust their perceptions and behaviours in response to improved electricity supply. The insignificant

relationship also suggests that short-term capital flight may be more driven by other structural problems in the economy such as corruption and political instability. Thus, the study identifies electricity supply as a long-term determinant of capital flight from Nigeria.

Regulatory quality (REQ), in conformity to its a priori expectation, showed negative and significant relationship with capital flight both in the short-run and in the long-run. The short-run coefficient of -0.8066 with its probability of 0.0001 implies that the estimate is significant at 1% level. This means that in the short-run, a unit increase in index of regulatory quality will reduce capital flight by 0.81% point. Also, the long-run coefficient of -0.4730 with the probability of 0.0674 shows the estimate is significant at 10% level. Thus, in the long-run, a unit increase in index of regulatory quality will reduce capital flight by 0.47% point. It can be deduced from the analysis that regulatory quality is a major determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. This means that improvement in regulatory quality leads to a reduction in capital flight from Nigeria. Thus, in the short-run, improved regulatory quality enhances investors' perceptions and confidence about Nigerian business environment and leads to a reduction in capital flight. The finding suggests that, in the long term, consistent and effective regulatory framework fosters stable business environment. High quality regulations promote economic growth, innovation and competitiveness thus making Nigerian business environment attractive to both local and foreign investors.

Corruption (COR) had negative relationship with capital flight in the short-run and in the long-run; in line with its a priori expectation. The negative a priori expectation was informed by the nature of the variable (COR). The index is based on the perceived levels of public sector corruption, scoring on a scale of 0 (highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean). Thus, by a priori expectation, a higher corruption perception index (implying lower level of corruption) is expected to reduce capital flight. The short-run coefficient of -0.5873, with its probability of 0.0029 shows that the estimate was significant at 1% level. Thus, in the short-run, a unit increase in corruption perception index reduced capital flight by 0.59% point. Similarly, the long-run coefficient of -0.6804 with its probability of 0.0747 shows that the estimate is significant at 10% level. This implies that in the long-run, a unit increase in corruption perception index reduced capital flight by 0.68% point. The results revealed that corruption is a strong determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. This finding supports the earlier finding by Tarawalie and Jalloh (2021). Reduced level of corruptions increases investors' trust in institutions, minimise rent-seeking and extortion; thus reducing business costs. In the long-run, consistent anti-corruption efforts can foster stable business environment, discourage money laundering activities and reduce incentives for capital flight.

External debt (EXD) exhibited a positive and significant short-run impact on capital flight (CAPF) whereas its long-run impact was positive but insignificant. The positive short-run and long-run impacts were in conformity to its a priori expectation. The short-run coefficient of 0.9335 with its probability of 0.0057 implies that the estimate is significant at 1% level. This means that in the short-run, 1% point increase in external debt increased capital flight by 0.93% point. The analysis revealed that EXD is a short-run determinant of CAPF from Nigeria. The analysis also revealed a positive relationship between external debt and capital flight from Nigeria; with a significant relationship in the short-run but insignificant one in the long-run. This means that in the short-run, increase in external debts is associated with increase in capital flight. The significant positive relationship in the short-run suggests that Nigeria's debt triggers immediate worries about the country's debt sustainability and

economic management which make investors to move their capital out of the country in order to safeguard their assets. This is because external borrowing comes with debt service burden and the fear of default, or potential depreciation of naira may exacerbate capital flight. This finding confirms the existence of debt-driven capital flight theory in Nigeria. While the said relationship persists in the long term, it is statistically insignificant because immediate impact of external debt on capital flight might diminish over time. In the long-run, the effects of external debt on capital flight may be moderated by factors such as economic reforms and better fiscal management. This finding is in agreement with the findings of many of the previous researchers such as Mazadu *et al.* (2022), Tarawalie and Jalloh (2021), Ndikumana and Boyce (2003), Dim and Ezenekwe (2014), Uddin *et al.* (2017), Azziz *et al.* (2014), Salandy and Henry (2018), Forson (2017), Aderibigbe (2019), but at opposing side to the findings of Fang *et al.* (2010) and Anetor (2019). This finding implies that external debt is a short-run determinant of capital flight from Nigeria.

An extract from the analysis is that regulatory quality (REQ) exhibited negative and significant relationship with capital flight in the short-run and in the long-run; indicating that improved regulatory quality reduces capital flight. Corruption (COR) showed negative and significant relationship with capital flight in the short-term and in the long term; and based on the nature of the variable as earlier discussed, implies that a reduction in corruption level reduces capital flight and vice versa. Inflation rate (INFR) exhibited positive and significant relationship with capital flight in the short-run and in the long-run; indicating that higher inflation rates leads to higher capital flight. Gross domestic product growth rate (GDPG) had a negative and significant relationship with capital flight only in the short-run; indicating that higher GDP growth reduces capital flight in the short-term. Exchange rate (EXR) exhibited negative and significant relationship with capital flight only in the short-run; indicating that naira depreciation reduces capital flight in the short-term. Index of electricity production (IEP) showed negative relationship with capital flight both in the short-run and in the long-run but only significant in the long-run; indicating that improved electricity supply reduces capital flight only in the long-term. External debt (EXD) had positive relationship with capital flight both in the short-run and in the long-run but only significant in the short-run; implying that higher external debt increased capital flight in the short-term.

Next, we examine the extent to which the system can adjust back to equilibrium after a shock using the coefficient of short-run adjustment term. The negative coefficient of short-run adjustment term of -0.6412 with its significant probability of 0.0000 implies that any short-run disequilibrium in the model is adjusted back to long-run equilibrium by the speed of 64% annually. This adjustment further confirms the earlier established co-integration among the variables in the model. The R-squared value of 0.9148 implies that the explanatory variables in the model jointly explain 91.5% of the variations in the dependent variable. This means that 91.5% of changes in capital flight from Nigeria within the period under study was explained by the joint-interactions of the explanatory variables in the model. Durbin-watson statistic value of 2.023 revealed that there was no autocorrelation in the model. We examined the overall significance of the model estimation using the F-statistic test. The F-statistic value of 12.593 with the probability of 0.0000 implies that the whole estimation is significant at 1% level and that findings from the model estimation can be used for policy prescriptions. Next, we assessed the reliability of the F-statistic estimate using some post estimation tests.

Table 5: Post Estimation Test Results

Test	F-Statistics	Probability
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey serial correlation LM Test	0.3758	0.6970
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	0.6918	0.7508
Jarque-Bera Normality Test	1.1425	0.5648
Ramsey RESET Functional Form Test	2.4787	0.1465

Source: Computed by the Researcher Using E-views 10.0 (2024)

The post estimation tests shown in Table 5 confirmed the reliability of the estimates for policy recommendations. Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation shows that there is no serial correlation in the residuals. This is judged from the probability of its F-statistic value of 0.6970 which is greater than 0.05. Also, Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test shows no evidence of heteroskedasticity; implying that the variance of the residuals are constant across observations. This can be seen from the insignificant probability of 0.7508 for its F-statistic. Jarque-Bera test shows that the residuals are normally distributed because the probability value of its F-statistic of 0.5648 is greater than 0.05; implying that there is no misspecification or outliers in the model. Similarly, the functional form test (RESET test) shows that the functional form of the model used is a good fit for the data set. This is judged from the insignificant probability of its F-statistic of 0.1465; implying that the model is well specified. Overall, the results indicate that the model passes all the tests due to the insignificant probabilities of the F-statistic in all the tests conducted. This confirms the reliability of the overall estimation.

Conclusion

The study revealed that economic, political and institutional factors influences capital flight from Nigeria. Regulatory quality, corruption and inflation rate are the major determinants of capital flight from Nigeria. GDP growth rate, exchange rate and external debt are viewed as short-run determinants of capital flight whereas electricity supply is a long-run determinant of capital flight from Nigeria. Addressing these determinants, particularly regulatory quality, corruption, and inflation rate can mitigate capital flight and enhance macroeconomic performance in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following policy recommendations are offered to curtail capital flight from Nigeria:

- (i) Governance and institutional frameworks should be strengthened by enhancing transparency and accountability in public finances. The government should enforce strict regulations in the banking system. Banks should be forced to follow the rules, including the 'Know Your Customer' (KYC) requirement in accepting public deposits. This should involve open reporting of suspicious financial transactions to the national authority. Any bank that defaults should be forced to pay a fine equal to the amount involved in such fraudulent transactions or have their operation license withdrawn. This will serve as a deterrent to other banks.
- (ii) The government should enact and implement strict anti-corruption and anti-money laundering policies that would deter people from capital flight and its related

activities. Anti-graft agencies such as Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) should be strengthened to improve their efforts in tackling money laundering and capital flight related practices. This should involve public prosecution and incarceration of offenders to serve as deterrents to others.

- (iii) Inflation should be controlled through aggressive industrialisation. Government should set up more industries and encourage private sector development in order to produce enough for domestic consumption and export. Adequate production level will stimulate the economy, bring down prices of goods and services, generate foreign exchange through exports, aid exchange rate appreciation and ultimately reduces incentive for capital flight.

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